

NOTES

TABLE 3—VISCOSITY PARAMETERS OF IRON COMPOUNDS IN 1-BUTANOL AT TEMPERATURES (35-50°)

Temp. in °C	Tested conc. range (moles litre ⁻¹)	Valid conc. range (moles litre ⁻¹)	\bar{V}	-Q	M	K'
			Lauryl sulphate			
35	0.001-.030	0.006-.030	3.91	12.77	1.11	125
40	.001-.030	.006-.030	10.14	12.17	1.23	138
45	.001-.030	.008-.030	15.66	9.89	1.33	200
50	.001-.030	.010-.030	31.32	7.36	1.53	212
			Laurate			
35	0.001-.020	0.008-.020	1.52	16.44	1.052	140
40	.001-.020	.008-.020	2.30	18.66	1.067	150
45	.001-.020	.006-.020	1.24	12.06	1.041	210
50	.001-.020	.006-.020	4.51	21.05	1.099	230

whereas other parameters (Table 3) for lauryl sulphate are higher than laurate at different temperatures.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to College authorities for providing laboratory facilities and to the UGC, New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

1. R. P. VARMA, K. SINGH and H. SINGH, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1978, **51**, 1530.
2. R. P. VARMA, H. K. BHARGAVA and R. DAYAL, *Ann. Soc. Chim. Polonorum.*, 1976, **30**, 307.
3. R. P. VARMA and H. K. BHARGAVA, *Ann. Chim.*, 1976, **66**, 773.
4. R. P. VARMA and K. KUMAR, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **54**, 156.
5. R. P. VARMA and K. KUMAR, *Colloid & Polym. Sci.*, 1978, **256**, 266.
6. R. P. VARMA and P. BAHADUR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 1189.
7. R. P. VARMA and K. KUMAR, *Cellulose Chem. Technol.*, 1975, **9**, 23.
8. V. VAND, *J. Phys. Colloid. Chem.*, 1948, **52**, 277.
9. S. P. MOULIK, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 4682.

Iodine Clock Oscillating Reaction

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Manuscript received 29 May 1978, revised 26 December 1979, accepted 9 April 1980

Briggs and Rauscher¹ reported a new oscillating reaction, viz., oscillating iodine clock reaction. The reaction gives striking and excellent cyclic changes from colorless to gold to blue using simple reagents (potassium iodate, hydrogen peroxide,

malonic acid, sulphuric or perchloric acid, manganese(II) or cerium(III) ion and starch) in proper concentrations. It resembles the iodate-hydrogen peroxide oscillating reaction of Bray-Liebhafsky^{2,4,5} and also uses manganese or cerium which are components of Belousov-Zhabotinsky^{3,4,5} reaction.

In this communication, the iodine clock oscillating reaction has been extensively studied using malonic acid and acetyl acetone in phosphoric acid medium. The concentration of each of the reactants has been systematically varied to determine the range of concentration where chemical oscillation is visible and to observe the resulting changes.

Three stock solutions are prepared separately and then mixed in equal volumes. One holds the hydrogen peroxide, another the iodate with phosphoric acid and the third, the malonic acid (or acetyl acetone), starch and manganese. This procedure has been changed when necessary and in all cases the concentrations in the table refer to concentrations in medium. The reaction mixture was continuously stirred at a more or less fixed rate with the help of a magnetic stirrer. The time period of oscillation was recorded visually.

Experimental

(Concentration ranges studied-See table)

Results and Discussion

In the sets (a) to (j) in the table, the following observations have been made.

- (a) With 0.0055(M) malonic acid—a few oscillations which are not sharp. With 0.011(M) and 0.022(M) concns.—time period decreases with time. With 0.188(M) concn.—colorless to golden oscillation.
- (b) With 0.073(M) H₂O₂—no visible oscillation. With 0.15(M) and higher concentrations—good oscillation.
- (c) With 0.043(M) KIO₃—no visible oscillation. With 0.046(M) and higher concns—good oscillation.

TABLE

	[Organic substrate*]	[H ₂ O ₂]	[KIO ₃]	[H ₃ PO ₄]	[Mn ⁺⁺]	[Starch]
a)	0.0055 (M) -0.188 (M)	1.2 (M)	0.0679 (M)	0.0426 (M)	0.0076 (M)	0.017%
b)	0.044 (M)	0.073 (M)	-do-	-do-	-do-	-do-
c)	-do-	-2.66 (M) 1.2 (M)	0.043 (M)	-do-	-do-	-do-
d)	0.0451 (M)	-do-	-0.061 (M) 0.065 (M)	0.0106 (M)	-do-	-do-
e)	-do-	-do-	-do-	-0.682 (M) 0.0426 (M)	0.0019 (M)	-do-
f)	0.0014 (M) -0.089 (M)	1.2 (M)	0.063 (M)	0.0853 (M)	-0.071 (M) 0.0066 (M)	0.0188%
g)	0.044 (M)	0.037 (M)	0.0615 (M)	-do-	-do-	0.0177%
h)	-do-	-1.66 (M) 1.2 (M)	0.031 (M)	-do-	0.071 (M)	0.023 %
i)	-do-	-do-	-0.062 (M) 0.0662 (M)	0.064 (M)	-do-	-do-
j)	-do-	-do-	0.063 (M)	-0.6824 (M) 0.0853 (M)	0.00166 (M) -0.22 (M)	0.0166%

* (a-e)-malonic acid
(f-j)-acetyl acetone

- (d) With 0.0106(M) H₃PO₄—colorless to golden oscillations which are not sharp. With higher concentrations, faint blue-deep blue oscillation. With 0.682(M) concn.—variation of intensity of blue color with time not sharp.
- (e) With 0.0019(M) Mn⁺⁺—color change not sharp. With 0.071(M) Mn⁺⁺—no observable oscillation. With intermediate concns.—good oscillation.
- (f) With concentration of acetyl acetone in the range 0.0014(M)—0.022(M), only 2-3 oscillations observed. With 0.044(M), 0.0533(M) and 0.062(M) concns.—good oscillation. With 0.089(M) concn.—no visible oscillation.
- (g) With 0.037(M) H₂O₂ as also with 1.66(M) H₂O₂—only 2 oscillations. With intermediate concns.—good oscillation.
- (h) With 0.031(M) and 0.0408(M) KIO₃—no observable oscillation. With 0.044(M) and higher concentrations—good oscillation.
- (i) With 0.064(M) H₃PO₄—no visible oscillation. With 0.6824(M) concn.—immediately blue precipitate. With intermediate concns.—good oscillation.
- (j) With 0.00166(M) Mn⁺⁺—2 or 3 oscillations. With higher concns.—good oscillation.

The observations support the earlier observations in general that oscillations are possible only in a certain range of concentrations. In the present investigations induction periods are practically nil (less than 1 min) and in certain cases only a few oscillations are possible. Excellent color changes take place from colorless to golden to blue. The golden color however, is not always detectable. Reappearance of blue color (in case of malonic acid) or disappearance of blue color (in case of acetyl acetone) was noted in recording the periods

of oscillation. In some cases, colorless to golden oscillation were recorded and in certain cases in later stages faint blue to deep blue oscillations were noted. In certain cases, the solutions become turbid and then oscillation starts. The time periods are of the order of a few seconds and the oscillations continue for several minutes. The oscillations are usually terminated by the appearance of a permanent blue color or precipitate. Time period gradually increases with time (decreases however in a few cases). In certain cases the increase in time period with time is remarkable.

Attempts have been made by different workers⁶⁻¹⁰ for elucidating the mechanisms of oscillatory reactions. In as much as no oscillating reaction is well understood at present, little can be said of the mechanism of the iodine clock. If malonic acid is not present, manganese or cerium catalyses¹ a rapid initial formation of iodine. Malonic acid is a halogen consumer and halide producer in both B-Z reaction and the oscillating iodine clock.

The reaction may be considered^{11,12} as switched rapidly between two steady states dependent on the iodide ion concentration and is thus composed of two gross phases.

A) The production of iodine via Mn(II) catalysed HIO₃-H₂O₂ reaction.

It would seem possible that a mechanism analogous to the HBrO₂ oxidation of Mn(II) in B-Z reaction is operative in the present case with consequent autocatalytic production of HIO₃ and subsequent rapid reduction of Mn(III) species by H₂O₂.

B) The consumption of iodine—iodide

The state responsible for production of iodine is dependent on the iodide concentration being low.

Thus as the iodide concentration rises there is reached a point when production of this state is inhibited and the iodine concentration no longer increases. Iodine, iodide and tri-iodide ions are now present and subject to at least four possible fates.

The principal consumption of iodine is via iodination of the organic species which is also the principal source of iodide ion. In the oscillatory system the iodination reaction together with the reoxidation of iodide produced maintains a steady state iodide concentration until the iodine concentration decreases appreciably. Eventually the iodide concentration decreases to a point where the production of the state responsible for production of iodine via the Mn(II) catalysed reaction is no longer inhibited, the remaining iodide is rapidly removed and the cycle commenced again. Thus the reaction can be regarded as a series of autocatalytic reaction 'bursts' occurring with a certain frequency.

We have to wait for sometime, however, for further elucidation of the mechanisms of these novel reactions.

References

1. T. S. BRIGGS and W. C. RAUSCHER, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1973, 50, 496.
 2. W. C. BRAY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 1262.
 3. B. P. BELOUSOV, Ref. Radiats. Med. 1958 (1958 collection of abstracts on Radiation Medicine, p-145, Medgiz, Moscow, 1959).
 4. R. M. NOYES and R. J. FIELD, *Ann. Rev. Phys. Chem.*, 1974, 25, 95.
 5. G. NICOLIS and J. PORTNOW, *Chem. Rev.*, 1973, 73, 365.
 6. R. M. NOYES, R. J. FIELD and E. KÖRÖS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 94, 1394.
 7. R. J. FIELD, E. KÖRÖS and R. M. NOYES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 94, 8649.
 8. G. SCHMITZ, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1977, 55, 3147.
 9. R. P. RASTOGI, P. RASTOGI and ASHWINI KUMAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, 15A, 163.
 10. R. M. NOYES and BAR-ELIK, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1977, 55, 3151.
- 1 D. O. COOKE, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1975, 3, 377.
 2 D. O. COOKE, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1976, 4, 329.

pH-Metric Studies of Schiff Base Complexes of Lanthanons

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Manuscript received 2 November 1979, accepted 20
December 1979

THE complexes of Pr(III), Nd(III), Gd(III) and Dy(III) with N-4-methylphenacylidene-O-aminophenol (MPAP) have been investigated by pH-metric titration technique as employed by Calvin and Melchior¹. The protonation constant of the ligand and the stepwise formation constants of the metal chelates have been evaluated at constant ionic strength 0.25M NaClO₄ and temperature 30 ± 1°.

Experimental

The ligand (MPAP) has been prepared and characterised by a similar method as reported earlier². Lanthanon/chlorides or nitrates (B.D.H) were dissolved in double distilled water. The solutions were estimated gravimetrically by precipitating the metal oxalates and subsequent ignition and weighing as metal oxides. The solutions of required strength were then prepared by suitable dilution. Potassium hydroxide (B. D. H.) was washed by methanol two or three times in order to ensure the removal of carbonate, if any and then dissolved in methanol to obtain stock solution and its strength was determined by using standard oxalic acid solution.

Conditions of Study :

The pH-metric titrations were carried out at 30 ± 1° with a Philips PP 9040 pH-meter as recommended by Zeidler³ and Fritz⁴.

The instrument was standardised against 0.05M solution of potassiumhydrogenphthalate. The volume of the solutions to be titrated was always kept constant (20 ml) by mixing with necessary volume of methanol. The following three mixtures (a), (b) & (c) were prepared for each system and titrated against standard alkali.

- (a) 10.0 ml of ligand (0.025M) + 5.0 ml of 1M NaClO₄
- (b) 10 ml of ligand (0.025M) + 5.0 ml of 1M NaClO₄ + 1.0 ml of metal salt solution (0.005 M).
- (c) 10.0 ml of ligand (0.025 M) + 5.0 ml of 1M NaClO₄ + 2.0 ml of metal salt solution (0.005 M).

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